

Orientalism and Historiography

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Received: 20 July, 2024 | Accepted: 02 September, 2024 | Published: 03 September, 2024

The word 'Orient' means 'East'. Here, one has to raise the first question- what of where is the 'East'? the earth is circular so, there is always land to the east. For example, I could say that the Americans are east of China and Japan. So, the word east becomes a relative term, when used in a purely geographical sense. Unfortunately, we do not use the word only in this strict sense, for linked with it is a whole world of conceptual meanings. In this conceptual world, 'the east' (with both 'T' and 'E' in capital), is not a relative, but a fixed term. It is to this fixed term that the word 'Orient' is added. 'Orient' then becomes, by itself, a conceptual category. In simple terms, the study of the orient is Orientalism. However, 'orientalism' implies a kind of analysis, a specific understanding, and therefore, a historical and historiographical study, and an area of study in itself.

Orientalism has been defined as "the theory and practice of representing 'the Orient'". It is not natural or objective, for it encompasses a world, in which reality is perceived, expressed and experienced as different. What needs to be remembered here, is that this perception begins with two fixed categories, of 'west' or 'Occident' and 'east' or 'Orient'. So, when one studies Orientalism, what one is basically looking at is a history of ideas, of the West about East. As said earlier, 'east' perhaps even more than west, is not a fixed term, for conceptual terms, it can be used to refer to any area that is not western Europe. It is therefore, something that can perhaps be called 'elsewhere'.

The Orient consists of primarily, the great Asian civilization of India, China and Japan, but orientalism, as an expression of perceptions of the east actually began with Islam. Obviously, all the terms that I am using are not monolithic categories, but the whole point of orientalism is that it treats them as such. Islam and the Crusades are the starting point of the construction of the Orient. In the writings of the time of the Crusades, one comes across the first representations of Muslims as evil, barbaric, ignorant, unclean, fanatical, violent, but ultimately inferior. Also from this time, 'west' began to be synonymous with Europe, more specifically, western Europe. So, orientalist approach is essentially a Eurocentric one. It constituted European civilization

as the yardstick by which Oriental cultures and civilizations were, and are measured. The only difference now, is that 'west' has expanded to include the former 'New World', America.

The next stage in orientalism comes from the Renaissance onwards, when the 'voyages of discovery' began. Cartography was an important aspect of the Renaissance, but in this period, it began with the premise that only those who 'discovered' had 'knowledge'. The world had always existed, but now, it was 'known'/ this knowledge gave mastery over the world, and so, Europe, which 'knew' the world, had a right to the world (and its produce, of course).

Linked to cartography was travel literature. This kind of literature, too, has a long history, for its ranges from the travel literature of the time of the crusades up to and including the era of colonialism. This genre of literature began with the premise of 'difference', but increasingly of difference expressed as inferior. Such literature was geared to an audience that had already some preconceived notions. So, the traveler tended to report that which his audience would expect him to talk about, not that which he actually saw.

The forces of the Renaissance and Reformation, and later the Enlightenment, furthered orientalism as a mentality. These forces required re-thinking the western framework as established until then. However, this rethinking was done on the basis of material available in the west, which comprised essentially the Bible and 'classics' - i.e., the heritage of Greece and Rome. From this time onwards, to use Ernest Gellner's phrase, the 'Orient' became the 'reserved laboratory' for testing western self-perception. So, for example, Arabic studies became important, so as to improve knowledge of ancient Hebrew, which was necessary for translating the Bible. Implicit in this is the idea which is the main theme of orientalism-that the language/s spoken in the 16th or 17th or 18th centuries in this orient were the same as spoken in these places at the time of Christ. In other words, there is a belief that the language did not change, because the societies had not changed. Change was thus made synonymous with progress, and so, orientalism served to prove that only the west progressed. Science, the spirit of scientific enquiry, rationalism, were the markers of this progress, and all existed only in the west.

If progress rested solely in the west, then the characteristic feature of the orient had to be tradition. Oriental scholars tended to emphasize this idea, of the orient being traditional. They therefore studied a past, and found in the living society the same past that they were studying. Sir William Jones, in the Indian context, is a classic example of this approach. He found in India's past and in Sanskrit, every proof of tradition that he looked for- whether it was the Gayatri mantra, or any other ritual of worship. The conclusion that could be drawn from this was obvious – that the traditions of the east were, at one and the same time, both living and dead: living, because they were still part of society and dead, because they were unchanging. Further proof of the latter was Sanskrit itself, a dead language.

The idea of 'discovery' was applied here too. What was discovered was the 'past', one which was then 'recovered' and given back to the 'natives'. For this, translation was necessary. The orientalists, especially of the 18th and 19th century, embarked on a whole series of translations, ranging from Nathaniel Halhed's translation of the Manava Dharma Sastra to Max Muller's Sacred Books of the East. A distinction was made between 'philosophic' Hinduism and 'popular' Hinduism, and the former was seen, especially in the 18th century, as a kind of undogmatic Protestantism. When, early in the 19th century, romanticism made its appearance, the same Hinduism was still seen as philosophic, but as mystic philosophy – one which was to be 'experienced', not understood. Romanticism looked eastwards with nostalgia. Themselves part of a fast changing industrial world, the romantics looked wistfully for changelessness, and found it in India. Once again, what is at the forefront is the idea of static societies. Missionaries, on the other hand, found in these static society's signs of decay. It was the work of the missionaries to change society, to do God's duty by bringing to the 'orient' all that it lacked. One level of the lack was being tackled through the political processes, as seen in the laws being passed by the colonial governments, but at another level, the missionaries had to step in. thus, 19th century orientalism saw a mix of evangelical and imperial ideas, all essentially concentrating on

the theme of progress – or rather, its lack. Such ideas were reinforced by the theory of race, which was also viewed as part of development.

It was tacitly accepted that, to bring about change, some knowledge was necessary. So, the earlier idea of ‘recovering’ the past now gained greater force. It was accepted that works of translation were enough to impart an understanding of the nature of Indian society, and so, it was entirely logical for Edmund Burke to urge, in 1781, that the British Parliament draft a bill, to be passed in England, for the protection of Indians in “the enjoyment of all those ancient laws and usages”.

Thus, to the entire construct of orientalism was now added one more layer, that of the sense of history. Tradition was distinct from history, so what existed in the ‘orient’ was only the former. History was a record of change, of progress, and as the orient lacked both, it was not surprising that there was no sense of history. Studies, of the Indian concept of time, the *yuga*, naturally added to this, for the *yuga* is conceived of as cyclical. It is against this background that one has to place what is even today called the first history of India, Mill’s History of British India, published in 1817. Not surprisingly, this became the textbook of Haileybury College, where the British administrators were taught. Philosophers like Hegel also played their part. Hegel saw history as having developed in four stages: the Oriental world, the Greek world, the Roman world and finally, the German world. Islam was part of the first, but Islam carried within it too much devotion to religion. Religion was, of course, irrational, and so, such societies were bound to ‘write themselves out of history’. Extreme dependence on religion meant that a civil society could not develop, and so, Oriental despotism was a logical result. This idea was picked up by Marx, as part of the Asiatic Mode of Production, as the characteristic of societies that did not have legal stability or enterprise or a bourgeoisie.

Colonial writing is the next clearly identifiable stage in orientalism. Earlier prejudices were reincarnated and given fresh empirical support in the reports of the colonial administrators, whether in India or elsewhere. Natives were stereotyped – a precursor to the later classification of the census – and so, we have phrases like ‘wily Brahman’, ‘stupid Egyptian’, ‘cunning Chinese’, etc.

The point that I have been trying to make is that orientalism is not just an approach or a perception, it is a mentality. The basic premise is that the Orient is an object, that can be analyzed, studied, and so understood. The problem arises from this very point, and so I go back to the question that I raised at the very beginning, but with a difference-what or a where is the ‘Orient? The Orient finally refers to everything that is not ‘western’, which unfortunately means the major portion of the world. And what is worse, the approach still exist -maybe not as clearly as in the 19th century, but unmistakable.

Critiques of orientalism began only in 20th century. Edward said is no doubt the most famous of the critics, but there were many others, who perhaps came up with sharper criticisms. A major problem that can still be seen is that the old ideas still persist. Take for example, Fukuyama’s *The End of History*, or Huntington’s *The Clash of Civilizations*. The former places history squarely in the capitalist world, which is the western world. So, logically, the collapse of the former Soviet bloc has to mean the triumph of that history which is meaningful, and the spread of that vision of history and progress alone. The political and economic collapse of the Soviet is proof that the methods of ‘The West’- meaning thereby the old ‘west’ comprising western Europe – is the only viable method. America then remains as the only power precisely because the mantle of western Europe has fallen on America. Huntington’s book, while on the surface challenging Fukoyama, in many ways reiterates the underlying assumption, of west as superior – the only difference is that, he puts in civilizational terms. Both are rooted in the idea of orient as ‘Other’ – and specifically, an ‘other’ that is passive, non-participant, and without sovereignty. One of the earliest critics of orientalism, Anouar Abdel-Malek, in a paper entitled, “Orientalism in Crisis”, identified four major components of the orientalist approach. The first component, he said, was the study of history. Central to this study was the theory that all oriental civilizations had a ‘golden age’, which lay in the past. So, the history of the orient was a history of decline from a specific starting point. Next, if glory lay in the past, then obviously the past could not be recovered, but the past could be studied in cultural and religious terms. Such terms were, naturally, not part of any evolutionary process,

because decline is not evolution. The study of Sanskrit then becomes even more justified, for it is a dead language, representing a dead past, and a stagnant present. History could easily be reduced to mere chronology – always keeping in mind that the orientals have no sense of time, and so, all the dates might be wrong. In any case, the calendars of the Orient also belonged to the dead past – it took the west (Switzerland, maybe!) to invent the pocket watch. The solar calendar, and the tabulation of time were specifically the possession of the west. Without such tabulation, time itself was meaningless (as it was to the west).

With all these limitations, the orientals could not study their own history. So, primary sources of all kinds -artifacts, documents, sculptures, paintings – were taken away and stored in the west, for that was where scholarship lay. What was left to the ‘native’ scholar was then colonial writing of different kinds, with all the associated problems.

As said earlier, Said’s work called *Orientalism*, is perhaps the most famous. Central to his argument is the concept of the ‘other’. Putting together much of the earlier critiques, he enunciated, in clear terms, the way in which the ‘orient’ had been created as the ‘dark underside’ of Europe. The orient was the mirror in which Europe was reflected, so that all that was present in Europe was identified what was missing in the Orient. Working through the methodology of literary criticism, he argued that the values of empire and imperialism permeated all the works of fiction of the time, including Jane Austen, Rudyard Kipling, Charles Dickens and Thomas Hardy. He in fact argued that the European novel itself was a result of imperialism. As imperialism was global, orientalism too went global, and so, in Said’s words, orientalism became the ‘grandest of all narratives’. He defined Orientalism as:

- 1) The classical tradition of studying a region by means of its languages and writings, so that anyone who researches, teaches or writes about the Orient is an Orientalist.
- 2) “A way of coming to terms with the Orient that is based on the Orient’s special place in European Western experience”.
- 3) A style of thought, with a very long historiography.
- 4) A method of domination, through epistemology, particularly.
- 5) A set of beliefs, prevalent among many who have never bothered to define the Orient in any clear way, but which creates an underlying unifying value structure.
- 6) A set of representations, which reinforced those structures.

The book thus presents what has been called a ‘genealogy of Orientalism’, “The Orient” is constant, but the geographical location of that orient changes according to the changing perceptions in the West. The entire book culminates in the way in which colonialism used all the earlier ideas, and restructured them into a system of domination and control. So, with colonialism, the orient was finally described, as lazy, or whatever term was seen as most applicable at a particular time.

Maybe because Said himself was part of the western academic world, the book raised a furore. Responses to it were immediate and varied. Some argued that orientalism was a discipline, which had nothing to do with politics, power, imperialism, or any other ‘ism’, for that matter. While there are undoubted problems with Said’s arguments, these criticisms obviously do not hold, for any critique of orientalist writing makes all the ‘isms’ very clear. A much more valid criticism is that Said himself tends to treat the Orient as a monolithic category, in much same fashion as the orientalists themselves. It also creates the west as a monolith, and so, the range of complexities that governed the relations between colonizer and colonized are not given adequate attention. It therefore permits no possibility of resistance to the ideas of orientalism itself.

I will now come to the question of orientalism in modern times – does it still exist? Or did it end with colonialism? I would argue that it is still present, and in many ways that we are only just beginning to understand. One major to be remembered is that colonialism and the responses to it shaped the world in which we now live. We are still dealing with the problems caused by partition, or the creation of Israel, or the issue of Hong Kong, from the intellectual approach of orientalism, which caused the problems in the first place? By separating the political from the ontological or epistemological, we are underlining the orientalist approach.

Globalization, it is said, is today inevitable. Obviously, we cannot argue with that, for we have travelled far along that path – but should we not also see that globalization is yet another manifestation of ideas prevalent from the time of Adam Smith? The point that I am trying to make is that Orientalism still exists, and as earlier, with the tacit acceptance of the orientals. I could maybe argue the emphasis on research into modern or ancient Indian History, at the cost of the medieval, is one more example of this kind of approach, for the modern was colonial, and the ancient was recovered by the colonial, while the medieval was denied.

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